

Disciplinary Commons Portfolio

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1 Context

1.1 The University

Coventry University is a large public UK university, a post-92, with over 40,000 students. The main campus is at Coventry (we also have campuses in London and Scarborough, as well as in Europe and further afield). Coventry has a reputation for high quality teaching, coming second in the UK in the 2017 Times Higher TEF (Teaching Excellence Framework) ranking, and for many years was in the Top 20 UK universities (Guardian Good University Guide). We are known for an applied, career-oriented approach with good industrial links and a strong placement service. We are also strong in transnational partnerships. 80% of our students are undergraduates, with a diverse and increasingly international student body (PG is strongly international).

1.2 The Courses

The University is structured as three colleges, each of which has several schools. The computer science suite of degrees is delivered by the School of Computing, Mathematics and Data Science in the College of Engineering, Environment and Science. I am responsible, as Curriculum lead, for a subset of these:

1.2.1 Undergraduate

- BSc / MSci Computer Science
- BSc / MSci Computer Science with Artificial Intelligence
- BSc Software Engineering

Undergraduates join us from diverse backgrounds in terms of nationality, culture, opportunity, and educational milieu. They may have significant prior programming expertise, or none. The vast majority are in the 18-21 age group, with only a handful of mature students each year. Our entry requirement across the suite for our BSc degrees is 120 UCAS points at A Level / BBB or equivalent (of which 40 must be in Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Further Maths,

Computer Science, Computing or Design Technology) as well as 5 GCSEs (4 of which must be at minimum C grade, and include Mathematics and English). These requirements can be significantly relaxed during clearing.

There is a wide ability range, and students also vary widely on motivation, from those who attend and engage with all we have to offer, to others we rarely see. A large section of the student body is instrumentally motivated and assessment-focussed, wanting to minimize time spent and maximize results. While we recognise this, and build necessary learning into assessment, this does mean students may neglect material which is not explicitly marked as assessable (or perceived as such). This presents a challenge, as it can lead to lower outcomes. The language of computer science is programming, which is at least as challenging and time consuming as a natural language to learn well and to excel at. Thus, we try to make teaching as attractive, engaging and intrinsically motivating as we can.

1.2.2 Postgraduate

- MSc Computer Science
- MSc Advanced Software Engineering
- BSc Artificial Intelligence and Human Factors

These postgraduate degrees are standalone. Few CU undergraduates progress onto these, especially since we have integrated MScs on two of our Undergraduate programmes. The student base is almost exclusively international.

1.3 How I came to be teaching computer science

I went to art school in the early 80s, and after a few years of working precariously in graphic design and photography decided to switch into teaching, spending several years teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL). In my early 30s I did an Open University degree in Psychology, becoming very interested in cognitive science and AI. That took me to the University of Sussex (their School of Cognitive and Computing Sciences) where I completed a Masters and a PhD. After this, I was a research fellow and lecturer at Sussex from 2000 to 2005. I moved to Coventry in 2006 for a Senior Lectureship and eventually became course leader on several programmes and then Curriculum Lead and Associate Professor in computer science.

I have now, over nearly 30 years, taught in many areas within or associated with CS, including HCI, UX, cognitive ergonomics, web development, software development, and programming. I teach less now, in a 60% management and curriculum development role - usually a single module each year. Until the academic year 24-25 I taught level 5 (2nd Year) Advanced Algorithms (an algorithms and data structures course). My main role is the development of curriculum and pedagogy. I have a special interest in pedagogy for programming generally, and algorithms specifically, hence my involvement in this Disciplinary Commons.

1.4 The Advanced Algorithms module

(NB ‘course’ at Coventry refers to degree; ‘module’ is the term we use and is used throughout this document.)

Advanced Algorithms is a Level 5 (Year 2) module on the following degrees (whose first two years, i.e. Levels 4 and 5, are common):

- BSc / MSci Computer Science
- BSc / MSci Computer Science with Artificial Intelligence
- BSc Software Engineering

Advanced Algorithms follows two Level 4 modules, Programming: Concepts and Algorithms (done in Python, starting at zero and ending with simple sorts and searches) and Programming: Professional Practice (OOP, version control, basic software, done in C++).

The syllabus for advanced algorithms appears as Figure 1 below. Its algorithmic / data structures content covers large parts of one of the standard texts, Cormen *et al* (2022). There are two assessments: coursework (CW) and exam. The coursework requires code solutions to a number of tasks (50%) as well a report which explains the code solutions (50%). Example tasks are included in the resource pack that accompanies this document (url at the end of the document). That makes explaining programming important on the module. This is taught with a wide range of examples (sample included in the resource pack), the purpose being to promote skills in accessibly describing what code does and how it works, evaluating quality, assessing alternatives and justifying decisions. These skills are about intellectual independence, critical evaluation, and communication, and are essential both academically and in industry.

The module prepares students for more demanding modules at Level 6 including Advanced Programming Paradigms (Haskell, Prolog, SAT/SMT solvers), Theoretical Aspects of Computer Science, and Parallel and Distributed Programming.

2 The Advanced Algorithms Module

2.1 Numbers

The module has around 100 - 150 students. It is a mandatory module for BSc Computer Science, BSc Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, and BSc Software Engineering.

2.2 Teaching and Learning

The module runs over 13 weeks, 12 of which are teaching weeks. In each week there is one 50 minute lecture, and two 50 minute labs (the labs run contiguously).

Materials are all digital and appear on the module page of Coventry University's VLE, Aula. These include lecture slides, recordings of lectures, worksheets, assessment specifications, FAQs, and a range of documents including a report template, manual worked examples of code and pseudocode, and examples of explanations of implementations of algorithms.

Teaching is designed to be interactive, student-centred and hands-on. Lectures are made as accessible as possible which implies that there should not be too much compression of material into available time (they are also designed to work as self-study, and there are additional self-study materials). Labs are based around a series of tasks. Early module (Weeks 1 - 3) tasks are not assessed and solutions are given 2 weeks later, including example explanations. From Week 4 students work on their portfolio of assessed tasks.

The module is staffed by two academics, one of whom is the module leader (ML). Each session whether lecture or lab has one academic.

2.3 Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

The module has the following objectives (intended learning outcomes):

On completion of this module the student should be able to:

1. Understand and select appropriate algorithms for solving a range of problems and reason about their complexity and efficiency.
2. Design and implement algorithms and data structures for novel problems.
3. Specify and implement methods to estimate solutions to intractable problems.
4. Describe the issue of data consistency in multi-threaded applications.
5. Design and implement a concurrent application.

2.4 Content and Syllabus

2.4.1 Content

Organisation: students take 6 13-week modules of 20 credits each per academic year / level. Advanced Algorithms is a 20-credit module in Semester 2 of their second year (Level 5). However the course discussed here is a forerunner of the current version, which was 15 credits.

2.4.2 Syllabus

(see Figure 1)

WEEK	DATE	TOPIC / EVENT	
1	16–20.01	Introduction Module structure and ILOs Assessment Introduction to algorithms	TEACHING WEEKS
2	23-27.01	Algorithms (1/4) Recursion Pseudocode Sorting: Insertion sort; bubble sort; merge sort; quick sort	
3	30.01-03.02	Algorithms (2/4) Searching: linear search; binary search; interpolation search Heaps: heap sort. Big O 1/3	
4	06–10.02	Data Structures (1/2) Trees: binary search tree; pre-order; in-order; post-order; breadth-first and depth-first; imbalanced trees; well-balanced tree; AVL trees.	
5	13-17.02	Data Structures (2/2) Graphs: types of graphs; undirected graph; directed graph; adjacency matrix; adjacency list; weighted graphs; graph traversal; connected graphs Hashes; hash tables	
6	20-24.02	Algorithms (3/4) Dijkstra’s algorithm; Prim’s algorithm; Bellman-Ford algorithm. Big O 2/3	
7	27.02-03.03	Algorithms (4/4) Greedy algorithms; Backtracking. Big O 3/3	
8	06-10.03	Complexity and Algorithms for NP-Hard problems (1/1) Review of Big O notation and algorithmic efficiency; Heuristics; Exhaustive search; Local search; GRASP; Simulated Annealing	
9	13-17.03	Concurrent and asynchronous applications (1/2) Programming with threads. Data sharing in multi-threaded environments.	
10	20-24.03	Concurrent and asynchronous applications (2/2) Asynchronous design patterns. Data consistency and program stability.	
11	27.03-31.04	Preparing your CW submission Exam past papers focus	
12	03-07.04	Exam Revision (TCA) CW submission	ASSESSMENT WEEKS
13	10-14.04	EXAM WEEK	

Figure 1: Advanced Algorithms: Syllabus

3 Methods and Teaching Philosophy

3.1 Philosophy

CU's teaching strategy states that teaching should be active, social, applied and inclusive.

In terms of *applied*, a former version of the current school pioneered what we call activity led learning (ALL), a form of problem based learning, which is concerned with embedding learning within meaningful activities, by virtue of being related to real-world problems (e.g. fixing code for Mozilla; finding the vulnerabilities in real code; collaborating to create a game whose scope is larger than a single person can deal with); or contextualised in real-world applications (e.g. binary search as a way to navigate directory structures). Students need to exercise initiative and develop problem solving skills, as well as attending and getting involved in teaching sessions (*active*). Teaching is *social* both in the constructionist sense (see below) as well as creating settings to leverage peer social interactions that support learning, and are also rewarding and pleasurable. *Inclusive* teaching and learning is about recognising different cultures and educational experiences, as well as responding to classes with a wide range of needs.

The formal teaching philosophy that guides this module as well as all the others on CS suite of computing degrees is constructionism (Papert & Harel, 1991; Laurillard, 2013). This theory holds that people learn best by doing, through a process of meaning-making involving interaction with resources around them, which may be artefacts or people. This implies that both students and teachers bring resources to learning, and that these need to be matched, consistent with Vygotsky's notions of scaffolding and zone of proximal development (see e.g. Karpov, 2014). Added to this is an approach we call 'affective' (Grawemeyer *et al*, 2022) which is concerned with how students feel about their learning. For example, we attempt to provide early success experiences to empower confidence, teach students to recognise success, to accept failure as part of the process and to develop resilience.

My own teaching philosophy, while aligned to the CU strategy and consistent with constructionism, can be summed up as 'what works is good'. I take an 'in the wild' approach (e.g. Rogers, 2017) concerned with the reality of everyday teaching and based on trying to understand and work with what is actually experienced and observed in our classrooms (complemented by, but not limited to, available statistics and learning analytics). This approach is structured around three dimensions: (1) content: the delivery of appropriate content relevant to intended learning outcomes; (2) student experience: especially passing first time, with good levels of satisfaction; and (3) student engagement: cognitive, affective and conative (following e.g. Snow and Farr, 1987). Cognitive means how far students understand what they are doing; affective how they feel about it; and conative their behaviours around learning. This term also connotes effort and orientation of behaviour to an outcome. Therefore, my teaching sessions involve observation and discussion with students as well as staff to try to gauge how far

students are on top of the material, feel OK about the module, and are involved in relevant activity towards positive outcomes. In a marketised and massified UK HE sector, none of this can be taken for granted, so this module, as well as the wider set for which I am responsible as curriculum lead, are part of wider effort to create a learning culture to attract and maximise engagement.

Advanced Algorithms is a programming module and as such generates particular challenges for students in terms of engagement and achievement. Algorithmic thinking, reasoning about programming, and communicating effectively and relevantly about programming are all substantial challenges, which feeds into Methods (next section).

3.2 Methods

Lecturing and labs are standard across most if not all modules on CS degrees at CU. Lectures have increasingly become formatted as self-contained instructional resources requiring no further research into what has been taught, and the teaching materials themselves made increasingly accessible, especially to non-mathematicians. This is all designed to address the needs of less able students, students without intrinsic motivation, and time pressured students (i.e., the majority). However the module also uses a RAG system in order to provide sufficient challenge to high fliers, those who are more intrinsically motivated and who are moving faster, or who have more experience as programmers.

Much use is made of visualisations of algorithms around worked examples, at first independent of implementations but later related to implementation, so that students can see what code relates to what part of a visually represented step-through of an algorithm, for example BST deletion where the delete node has two children, or the selection of the next node for a shortest path algorithm (examples of these materials are included in the resource pack, at the end of this document).

R (and A) tasks are more difficult in terms of scale, complexity, and required knowledge of programming and data structures. These tasks may require students to think about fundamentals, for example choice of programming language, construct(s) and even data structure, for example whether Dijkstra's algorithm could or should be written using a priority queue. R tasks may also present challenge in terms of explanation, for example familiar recursive algorithms such as 8 Queens or Towers of Hanoi where the challenge is not so much to code the solutions (which are already out there), but to explain how and why they work.

In constructionist terms, then, teaching materials tend to respond to a situation where students may bring less in terms of resourcing, where we need to provide more in response. This also goes for lab sessions where a pro-active staff approach implies that we do not wait for enquiries, for example, but look for opportunities to support. Staff need to be pleasant and approachable and not perceived as 'policing' the room, but at the same time we need to challenge (and where necessary stop) irrelevant or disruptive behaviour, as well as avoidance behaviours and 'empty avatar' behaviour where the student is present simply to

be recorded as attending but not involved in relevant activity. Many students attempt to hide a lack of confidence / ability / study skills and for this reason the module is informed by a zero credit 'meta-module' called Course Level Learning which is about what University involves, how to develop the skills, what support will be provided, with messages including failure is not only allowed but can be positive, and that teaching sessions are safe spaces.

4 Assessment and Evidence of Student Learning

It seems undoubtedly to be the case in current UK HE that the main concern for the majority of students is assessment. What learning students will engage in has to be perceived to have clear value for assessment results – i.e., grades, and ultimately degree class.

Therefore, assessment has to be thought about along a number of dimensions. One of these is that it has to fit relevant HE descriptors and benchmarks, which we represent with our ILOs (Intended Learning Outcomes). Another is that it should promote relevant employable and transferrable skills. A further key consideration is that assessment has to be designed to try to ensure learning that is regarded as essential assuming the student wants a good degree, as well as employment in the field; in other words, there need to be clear messages that all core material is assessable, to produce engagement.

This latter approach can be criticised, summed up in the phrase 'we do not [or should not] teach to assessment'. The ideal is that assessment is a checkpoint or milestone in a journey / process that is happening anyway; i.e. that there is a program of activity unfolding whether or not it is assessed, similar to employment.

However, we can no longer assume this, so at CU assessment focus has been embraced and we have a policy called Assessment First: students are explicitly told what the assessment is on the first day, and then, later, how every piece of content and every learning session bears on assessment. The Course Level Learning program embeds assessment in a narrative about the larger aims of assessment: to take students on a transformative journey, helping them grow, and do well at work and in life.

There are examples of the assessment we set in the resource pack (at the end of this document).

The embedding of checking for student learning is now well established at CU and we do this in a number of ways:

- Q & A, quizzes, competitions (which group can find solutions fastest), online polls (MCQs with the distribution of answers shown as a graph) - or some mix of these
- using 1-to-1 lab time with students to talk through their problems, issues and challenges; and encourage them to explain their work and the support they need

- observation and involvement in peer teaching and learning (where students spontaneously form self-help groups in class and work collaboratively)
- core assessment: this is pass/fail assessment with 3 attempts worth a proportion of total module credit, which we apply in the first year

4.1 Student Support

The support we offer as a routine part of teaching is part of a wider support ecology. We also offer:

- ML / staff office hours (2 hour sessions each week with bookable 1-to-1 slots). These must be held in the DLC (see below)
- 'Digital Literacy Centre' (DLC) a purpose made drop-in centre which offers programming support all day every day from staff and student proctors
- Student Success Coaches specifically employed by CU to support students on a range of issues not just academic
- Course Level Learning, a 'meta-module' about what University is, what's expected, how it works and how to do well
- Personal Tutor
- Theta and Sigma Centres. Theta is a general purpose drop-in additional to DLC (which can get full); and Sigma is a drop-in for maths support. Like DLC these are staffed all day every day

5 Explaining and Critiquing Programming

One of the most highly-prized abilities, both in academia and industry, is to be able to select, develop / find, critically reflect on, and justify, solutions to problems. This implies that people can explain what the problem is, how they have approached it, what they have done, and why they have done it that way.

On Advanced Algorithms, and across programming modules more broadly, we are introducing and teaching code documentation standards, and we are also teaching how to explain programming.

This is to promote student confidence, knowledge, articulacy, and critical skills, and to make sure this is safeguarded, mitigating against code plagiarism and other non-student-generated content that is now possible via generative AI (aka large language models, and products like chatGPT, Bard, etc.) while we are still researching what value this latter might deliver in terms of learning.

As a faculty we believe that intelligence is human, and the kinds of knowledge, creativity and critical skills required in academia, industry and professional life cannot be replicated by / substituted for AI. (NB a discussion of the nature and limitations of generative AI is beyond the scope of this document.)

This is leading to a raft of new integrated teaching which is not only about being able to code, but being able to explain it, both verbally and in writing. Advanced Algorithms is one of the main modules where this is being embedded.

Below, there is more material on how we are approaching this.

5.1 Assessment Materials

The Advanced Algorithms module is assessed by a portfolio of coursework, and a TCA (Time Constrained Assessment). Examples of each appear in the resource pack.

6 Resource Pack

6.1 Assessment Material (1): Coursework

Two example tasks at different levels of difficulty:

5003CEM

Advanced Algorithms

Week 5

ASSESSED LAB TASK: STD_2

Introduction (Recap)

5003CEM is assessed by coursework (10/15 credits) and exam (5/15 credits).

For the coursework, you need to submit a portfolio of work you've completed each week in the labs (and in your own time outside the labs).

Each week, there will be up to 4 types of task:

Non-assessed	Assessed
Standard	Standard
Non-assessed	Assessed
Advanced	Advanced

In Week 12, you'll need to submit ALL the assessed standard and assessed advanced tasks. There will be FIVE standard assessed tasks and THREE advanced assessed tasks. Assessed tasks will be evenly spaced across the module from Weeks 4 to 9.

There is no weekly deadline for assessed tasks; they are all part of your coursework, to be submitted on Thursday 4 April, 18:00. But it's a good idea to try to complete the assessed tasks in a timely way, so that they don't build up.

ASSESSED STANDARD TASK 2/5

Assessed Standard Task 2/5: Find method for Binary Tree class

Standard

From the pseudocode given in the lecture slides for Week 4, Data Structures 1, Slides 115 to 119, create 2 binary search methods, one iterative and one recursive, and implement these into the python Binary Tree class given on this week's Aula in the zip folder, 'BST-class'.

Call the iterative method `find_i`, and the recursive method `find_r`. Notice that `find_r` needs a sub-method. Call this `_find_r`.

Each method should return `True`, `False`, or `None` (note that the solution for 'None' is not given in the iterative pseudocode).

Add comments to show your understanding.

Check your code works by calling it and returning the correct result.

You may decide, if you wish, to implement the entire class and solutions in C++, instead of, or in addition to, the python solution, but this is not mandatory for this task.

5003CEM

Advanced Algorithms

Week 5

ASSESSED LAB TASK: ADV_1

Introduction (Recap)

5003CEM is assessed by coursework (10/15 credits) and exam (5/15 credits).

For the coursework, you need to submit a portfolio of work you've completed each week in the labs (and in your own time outside the labs).

Each week, there will be up to 4 types of task:

Non-assessed Standard	Assessed Standard
Non-assessed Advanced	Assessed Advanced

In Week 12, you'll need to submit ALL the assessed standard and assessed advanced tasks. There will be FIVE standard assessed tasks and THREE advanced assessed tasks. Assessed tasks will be evenly spaced across the module from Weeks 4 to 9.

There is no weekly deadline for assessed tasks; they are all part of your coursework, to be submitted on Thursday 4 April, 18:00. But it's a good idea to try to complete the assessed tasks in a timely way, so that they don't build up.

ASSESSED ADVANCED TASK 1/3

Assessed Advanced Task 1/3: Remove method for Binary Tree class

Advanced

From the partial pseudocode given below (one case is omitted), implement an iterative method called `remove` which deletes a node and reorganises the tree. There are indications where the pseudocode is missing. NB the pseudocode crosses pages.

Add comments to show your understanding.

Implement your solution into the python Binary Tree class given on this week's Aula in the zip folder, 'BST-class'.

Make sure that `remove` works correctly; that is, not only is the target node deleted, but the tree is also correctly re-organised. If not, it may mean the pseudocode needs some detail adding.

You may decide, if you wish, to implement the entire class and solution in C++ instead of, or in addition to, the python solution, but this is not mandatory for this task.

```
REMOVE(tree, target)
    IF tree.root IS None                                //if no tree
        RETURN False
    ELSE IF tree.root.data = target                    //if tree root is target
        IF tree.root.left IS None AND tree.root.right IS None
            tree.root ← None
        ELSE IF tree.root.left AND tree.root.right IS None
            tree.root ← tree.root.left
        ELSE IF tree.root.left IS None AND tree.root.right
            tree.root ← tree.root.right
        ELSE IF tree.root.left AND tree.root.right
            IF_LEFT_AND_RIGHT(tree.root)
```

(continues over)

```

//if root is not target
parent ← None
node ← tree.root

WHILE node and node.data != target
    parent ← node
    IF target < node.data
        node ← node.left
    ELSE IF target > node.data
        node ← node.right

IF node IS None OR node.data != target           //CASE 1: Target not found
    RETURN False                                 //for info only (we could not find it)

ELSE IF node.left IS None AND node.right IS None //CASE 2: Target has no children
    IF target < parent.data
        parent.left ← None
    ELSE
        parent.right ← None
    RETURN True                                 //info only

ELSE IF node.left AND node.right IS None        //CASE 3: Target has left child only
    IF target < parent.data
        parent.left ← node.left
    ELSE
        parent.right ← node.left
    RETURN True                                 //info only

NOT IMPLEMENTED                                 //CASE 4: Target has right child only

ELSE                                             //CASE 5: Target has left and right children
    IF_LEFT_AND_RIGHT(node)

```

(continues over)

```

IF_LEFT_AND_RIGHT(node)                                //called if delete node whether root or otherwise
  delNodeParent ← node                                  //has left and right children
  delNode = node.right

  WHILE delNode.left
    delNodeParent ← delNode
    delNode ← delNode.left

  node.data ← delNode.data

  IF delNode.right
    IF delNodeParent.data > delNode.data
      delNodeParent.left ← delNode.right
    ELSE
      delNodeParent.right ← delNode.right

  ELSE
    IF delNode.data < delNodeParent.data
      delNodeParent.left ← None
    ELSE
      delNodeParent.right ← None

```

6.2 Assessment Material (2): Time Constrained Assessment

An example question (over):

SAMPLE TCA QUESTION. A file containing the code for part (c) is provided to students

Question 3

Total for Question 3: **25 Marks**

- a) Using Graph 1, apply Kruskal's algorithm, produce an ascending list of 5 edges. The first has been done for you. (4 marks)

Graph 1

Node	Weight	Node
0	1	1

- b) Explain the cycle problem in Kruskal's algorithm, and indicate which edge or edges would not be included in the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST), due to the need to avoid cycles. Use an example to illustrate your answer. (8 Marks)

Question 3 continues on the next page

Question 3 continued

- c) Complete the Python code below so that Kruskal's algorithm is correctly implemented to avoid cycles. You only need to write the lines where comments have been added to support your solution. Note that this code is available with this TCA as Q3c.py, inside the folder 5003CEM_TCA_CODE.zip: Use this file to create your solution. Paste your code here (correctly formatted; only the missing code is needed). Additionally submit it along with this paper with its original name Q3c.py, inside a zip folder called name_SID_5003CEM_CODE.zip..

(13 marks)

```
from collections import defaultdict

class Graph:

    def __init__(self, vertices):
        self.V= vertices
        self.graph = []

    def addEdge(self, u, v, w):
        self.graph.append([u, v, w])

    ''' find set of an element i '''
    def find(self, parent, i):
        if parent[i] == i:
            return i
        return self.find(parent, parent[i])

    ''' union of two sets of x and y '''
    ''' restructures parent and rank lists '''
    def union(self, parent, rank, x, y):
        xroot = self.find(parent, x)
        yroot = self.find(parent, y)
        if rank[xroot] < rank[yroot]:
            parent[xroot] = yroot
        elif rank[xroot] > rank[yroot]:
            parent[yroot] = xroot
        else:
            parent[yroot] = xroot
            rank[xroot] += 1
```

Question 3 continues on the next page

Question 3 continued

```
''' function to build MST using Kruskal's algorithm '''
def KruskalMST(self):
    result = []
    i = 0
    e = 0
    self.graph = sorted(self.graph, key=lambda item: item[2])
    parent = []
    rank = []
    for node in range(self.V):
        parent.append(node)
        rank.append(0)
    while e < self.V - 1:
        u, v, w = self.graph[i]
        i = i + 1
        x = self.find(parent, u)
        y = self.find(parent, v)
        #check for cycle: if u and v have diff parents
        #COMPLETE #increment e
        #CODE #append u, v and w to result
        #HERE #do union of parent and rank lists with x and y
        #if x and y are equal, edge is discarded
    print ("The edges in the MST are:")
    for u, v, weight in result:
        print ("%d -- %d == %d" % (u, v, weight))

g = Graph(4)
g.addEdge(0, 1, 1)
g.addEdge(0, 2, 2)
g.addEdge(0, 3, 6)
g.addEdge(1, 3, 4)
g.addEdge(2, 3, 3)
```

6.3 Teaching Material

A full lecture on binary search trees exemplifying animation approach (begins over):

5003CEM Advanced Algorithms

Data Structures 1: Binary Trees

John Halloran | Beate Grawemeyer

What is a Data Structure?

- A data structure enables:
 - Data storage
 - Data organization
 - Data management
- These allow:
 - Easier, more efficient data access
 - Easier, more efficient data search / insertion / deletion

Binary Trees / Heaps (last week)

- We have started to look at
 - Binary Trees
 - Heaps
- A heap is a type of binary tree
- Arrangement of data as trees speeds up search by reducing the number of operations necessary to find a target
- They allow efficient
 - Search (finding a value)
 - Deleting
 - Inserting

Data Structures 1

- Expand your understanding of **trees**:
unbalanced trees | well-balanced trees |
AVL trees
- Understand types of tree traversal:
pre-order | in-order | post-order
- Understand further searches:
breadth-first | depth-first

Trees

- Let's build on what we started last week
- A tree has
 - root
 - parent
 - child / branch
 - leaf

Trees

root (i.e., top of the tree; nothing above it)

Trees

Trees

Trees

Binary Tree: Rules 1

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater
- Let's check this!

Binary Tree

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater
- Let's check this!

Binary Tree

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater
- Let's check this!

Binary Tree

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater
- Let's check this!

Left subtree: less than parent = 8

Binary Tree

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less than the value of the node.
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater than the value of the node.
- Let's check this!

Left subtree: less than parent = 3

Left subtree: less than parent = 8

Binary Tree

- For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less than the value of the node.
- For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater than the value of the node.
- Let's check this!

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the left must be less than any value on the right

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the left must be less than any value on the right

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the left must be less than any value on the right

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the right must be greater than any value on the left

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the right must be greater than any value on the left

Binary Tree: Emergent Property

- Any value on the right must be greater than any value on the left

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

- We want to insert 9
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1:

Insert

- We want to insert 9
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

- We want to insert 9
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

- We want to insert 9
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

- We want to insert 9
- Where should it go?

So insert 9 to the
left of 12

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

- Now we want to insert 2
- Where should it go?
- See if you can work this out

Operations on Binary Trees 1:

Insert

- Now we want to insert 2
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

Move down.
 $2 < 3$ so it goes on the left

- Now we want to insert 2
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

Move down again.
 $2 > 1$ so it goes on the
right

- Now we want to insert 2
- Where should it go?

Operations on Binary Trees 1: Insert

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We want to delete 12
- How?

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We want to delete 12
- How?
- Easy. Remove it.

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Why was this easy?
- Remember the rules:
 - For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
 - For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Remember the rules:
 - For each node, the value of all nodes in its left subtree must be less
 - For each node, the value of all nodes in its right subtree must be greater
- The new tree observes these rules

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- So, deleting any leaf node preserves the BST (Binary Search Tree)
- It is preserved because a BST must follow the 2 rules
- And deleting a leaf node means the rules are observed
- So we don't need to do anything else to the BST

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Here's the BST with inserted 9
- Now we want to delete 12
- How? This BST is different; 12 has a child (9)

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- But if we cut the link to 12 here...
- ... we will lose everything below it...
- ... including the 9!

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We need to attach what will be the new parent of 9, to 9

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We need to attach what will be the new parent of 9, to 9
- Then remove 12

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We need to attach what will be the new parent of 9, to 9
- Then remove 12...
- ... to give us the new tree

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Now, looking again at the original BST
- We now want to delete 8
- But hold on – it has TWO children, 6 and 12

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- If we cut this link...

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- If we cut this link...
- ... we'll lose the entire right side subtree!

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- So what we need to do is not remove the node...

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- So what we need to do is not remove the node...
- ... but remove its data

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- We need to look for the minimum value in the right subtree of the node...
- ... which is 12 (there is no other value)

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Copy the data to the empty node

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Copy the data to the empty node...
- ... and delete the leaf

Operations on Binary Trees 2: Delete

- Copy the data to the empty node...
- ... and delete the leaf
- Done. Check for yourself that the rules apply.

BST Deletion: a more complex example

This means **Binary Search Tree** (the point of this data structure – more later in this lecture)

- This one has 3 new leaves
- We want to delete 8 again
- How?

BST Deletion: a more complex example

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

- Minimum value in the right:
 - Move rightwards of the delete node
 - Move left as far as you can go. That is the lowest value (11)

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

- Maximum value in the left:
 - Move leftwards of the delete node
 - Move right as far as you can go. That is the highest value (7)

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

- Maximum value in the left:
 - Copy maximum value to the delete node

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

- Minimum value in the right:
 - Move rightwards of the delete node
 - Move left as far as you can go. That is the lowest value
 - What would this be, and what would be the process to reorganize the tree?

BST Deletion: rule where there are two children

- Maximum value in the left:
 - Move leftwards of the delete node
 - Move right as far as you can go. That is the highest value
 - What would this be, and what would be the process to reorganize the tree?

BST Deletion Cases

- CASE 1: no child
- CASE 2: one child
- CASE 3: two children
- If Case 2 or 3, the children can have their own children
- Case 1 is easy; the others are more complex
 - They involve new parent – child relationships
 - They can involve copying values prior to deletion
- So deletion often involves tree reconfiguration

BST Traversal

- There are different ways to 'travel' (traverse) a BST
- These are:
 - Pre order
 - In order
 - Post order

BST Traversal: Pre Order

- Start at the root
- Follow left tree
- Then follow right tree

BST Traversal: Pre Order

- Start at the root
- Follow left tree
- Then follow right tree

[10, 8, 5, 9, 14, 12, 11, 13, 17]

Pre Order Pseudocode

PREORDER(cur_node):

 PRINT cur_node.value

 IF cur_node.left \neq 0:

 PREORDER (cur_node.left)

 IF cur_node.right \neq 0:

 PREORDER (cur_node.right)

BST Traversal: In Order

- For each node, display
 - The left child
 - The node
 - The right child
- When displaying the left or right, follow the same instruction

BST Traversal: In Order

- For each node, display
 - The left child
 - The node
 - The right child

[5, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 17]

In Order Pseudocode

INORDER(tree):

IF tree.left \neq 0:

 INORDER(tree.left)

 PRINT tree.value

IF tree.right \neq 0:

 INORDER(tree.right)

BST Traversal: Post Order

- For each node
 - Follow the left child
 - Follow the right child
 - Display the node

BST Traversal: Post Order

- For each node
 - Follow the left child
 - Follow the right child
 - Display the node

[5, 9, 8, 11, 13, 12, 17, 14, 10]

Post Order Pseudocode

POSTORDER(tree):

 IF tree.left \neq 0:

 POSTORDER (tree.left)

 IF tree.right \neq 0:

 POSTORDER (tree.right)

 PRINT tree.value

When to / Why use different kinds of traversal

Pre order

- if you know you need to explore roots before leaves
- Also, replicates a tree

Post order

- if you know you need to explore leaves before roots
- Also, to delete a tree from leaves to root

In order

- if you know you need to 'flatten' the tree, i.e. show all the nodes in sequence

Breadth First Search

- Start with the root and proceed in order of increasing depth, as if reading:
 - Top-to-bottom, left-to-right

[10, 8, 14, 5, 9, 12, 17, 11, 13]

Breadth First Search

- Start with the root and proceed in order of increasing depth, as if reading:
 - Top-to-bottom, left-to-right

[10, 8, 14, 5, 9, 12, 17, 11, 13]

Depth First Search

- Start with the root, move down as far as you can go, then move right:

[10, 8, 5, 9, 14, 12, 11, 13, 17]

Depth First Search

- Start with the root, move down as far as you can go, then move right:

[10, 8, 5, 9, 14, 12, 11, 13, 17]

When / Why use Depth First or Breadth First

- BFS is good for balanced trees
- DFS is good for unbalanced trees
- We'll come back to that shortly
- BUT – there's a better way: **binary search trees**

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

- How would we search for 12?

Binary Search T

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient

12 > root, so move right

- How would we search for 12?

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient

12 > 8, so move right

- How would we search for 12?

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

- How would we search for 12?

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

- $n = 7$; 3 comparisons to find target

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

- As n increases, operations stay constant

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search

Level 2
 $n = 4$;
comparison = 1

Binary Search Trees

- BSTs allow powerful, efficient search: $\log(n)$

Level 2
 $n = 4$;
comparison = 1

Binary Search Trees

- A perfectly balanced tree will always give us one comparison per level regardless of the size of the tree
- Comparisons as % of n will always decrease

Binary Search Trees

- This means we need to start thinking about what happens when trees are unbalanced
- And what we can do about it

Balanced Tree

- We want to find 6: BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 7: BFS or DFS?

Balanced Tree

- We want to find 6: BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 7: BFS or DFS?

BFS: 4, 2, 6
DFS: 4, 2, 1, 3, 6

BFS: 4, 2, 6, 1, 3, 5, 7
DFS: 4, 2, 1, 3, 6, 5, 7

Unbalanced Tree

- We want to find 6
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 20
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 32
 - BFS or DFS?

Unbalanced Tree

- We want to find 6
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 20
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 32
 - BFS or DFS?

BFS: 4, 2, 8, 1, 5, 10, 7, 9, 18, 6
DFS: 4, 2, 1, 8, 5, 7, 6

Unbalanced Tree

- We want to find 6
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 20
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 32
 - BFS or DFS?

BFS: 4, 2, 8, 1, 5, 10, 7, 9, 18, 6, 50, 32, 100, 20
DFS: 4, 2, 1, 8, 5, 7, 6, 10, 9, 18, 50, 32, 20

Unbalanced Tree

- We want to find 6
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 20
 - BFS or DFS?
- We want to find 32
 - BFS or DFS?

BFS: 4, 2, 8, 1, 5, 10, 7, 9, 18, 6, 50, 32

DFS: 4, 2, 1, 8, 5, 7, 6, 10, 9, 18, 50, 32

Topology

- Choosing BFS or DFS depends on topology
 - If we don't know...
 - ...choose either.

The Problem

- Standard BST insertion rules can give us unbalanced trees
- The tree on the right is result of [4,2,6,1,2,5,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15, 100,200] using standard insertion
- Issue is that while search up to 7 is $\log n$, after 7 it is n (i.e. linear)
- This defeats the purpose of a BST, which is to enable binary search in $\log n$ time

Unbalanced Trees

Balanced

Unbalanced

Unbalanced Trees

Balanced

Unbalanced

Target = 20

What is n at each level?

How many comparisons in total?

Unbalanced Trees

Balanced

Unbalanced

Target = 20
n = 17
comparisons = 7

Balancing an unbalanced tree

Unbalanced

Balanced

Balancing an unbalanced tree

A really unbalanced tree!

Balanced

Unbalanced

REALLY unbalanced

Here, finding any item is $O(n)$

A really unbalanced tree!

Balanced

Unbalanced

REALLY unbalanced

No better than linear search

Here, finding any item is $O(n)$

A really unbalanced tree!

Balanced

Unbalanced

REALLY unbalanced

If we want to leverage the power of BST, we have to balance the tree

No better than linear search

Here, finding any item is $O(n)$

Solution

- The solution is to balance the tree as we insert, rebalancing the tree as we go
- This is what AVL Trees achieve
- First we need to look at tree height

Tree height

Node height

Node height

So is the height of this node 1 or 2?

Node height is max of height(left child), height (right child) +1

Node height

Height Rule for AVL Trees

- AVL trees require heights of left and right children of every node to differ by at most ± 1
- AVL Trees are balanced
- Worst case is when one subtree has 1 more than the other for every node

Worst Case AVL Tree

Worst Case AVL Tree: node heights

Hold on. Why does this jump from 0 to 2, then 2 to 4, on the left?

Worst Case AVL Tree: node heights

Hold on. Why does this jump from 0 to 2, then 2 to 4, on the left?

We need to remember the node height rule...

Worst Case AVL Tree: node heights

Hold on. Why does this jump from 0 to 2, then 2 to 4, on the left?

We need to remember the node height rule...

... node height is max of height(left child), height (right child) +1

Insert to build

- In theory it is possible to rebalance an existing tree
- But it makes more sense to balance as we build
- The simplest solution given an unbalanced tree is to flatten it and then reconstruct
- Applying AVL on insertion means the tree can never be unbalanced
- This section explains how that happens

Insert to build

- In theory it is possible to rebalance an existing tree
- But it makes more build
- The simplest solution given an unbalanced tree is to flatten it and then reconstruct
- Applying AVL on insertion means the tree can never be unbalanced
- This section explains how that happens

How do we flatten a tree? See Lecture from Week 4 on traversals

Algorithm

1. Simple BST insert
2. Fix AVL property from inserted node up

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26]

AVL OK

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23]

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23]

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23]

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23]

BST Insert

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23]

Single Rotation

Single Rotation

Single Rotation

Single Rotation

Then rotating the highest value to the right

Single Rotation

Double Rotation

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23, 55]

Double Rotation

[41, 20, 65, 11, 29, 50, 26, 23, 55]

Double Rotation

Even though the left and right subtrees of the root are the same height, we have broken our AVL rule: AVL trees require heights of left and right children of **every** node to differ by at most ± 1 . For this instance, the difference is 2.

AVL NOT OK!!
DOUBLE LEFT
HEAVY

Double Rotation

Double Rotation

Values are wrong: we cannot have a left child value greater than its parent

Single right rotation will not work!

Double Rotation

1. Rotate subtree

Double Rotation

1. Rotate subtree

Double Rotation

2. Rotate path

Double Rotation

4 cases

- Double left heavy
- Double right heavy
- Left-right heavy
- Right-left heavy
- Look back at the examples above
 - Which cases are these?

4 cases

- Double left heavy
- Double right heavy
- Left-right heavy
- Right-left heavy

Slides 43 - 47

Slides 54 - 57

4 cases

- Double left heavy
- Double right heavy
- Left-right heavy
- Right-left heavy

Slides 43 - 47

Slides 54 - 57

Double right is mirror of double
left
Left-right is mirror of right-left

High Level Pseudocode

IF tree is right heavy

IF tree's right subtree is left heavy

Perform Double Left Rotation

ELSE Perform Single Left Rotation

ELSE IF tree is left heavy

IF tree's left subtree is right heavy

Perform Double Right Rotation

ELSE Perform Single Right Rotation

Check Balance Pseudocode

CHECK_BALANCE(tree):

lsize \leftarrow 0 rsize \leftarrow 0

IF tree.left \neq 0:

 lsize \leftarrow tree.left.depth

IF tree.right \neq 0:

 rsize \leftarrow tree.right.depth

RETURN rsize-lsize

Implementing a BST

- Basic python code for creating a tree:

```
class Node(object):  
    def __init__(self, value):  
        self.value = value  
        self.left = None  
        self.right = None
```

```
class BinaryTree(object):  
    def __init__(self, root):  
        self.root = Node.root
```

```
tree = BinaryTree(1)  
tree.root.left = Node(2)  
tree.root.right = Node(3)  
tree.root.left.left = Node(4)  
tree.root.left.right = Node(5)  
tree.root.right.left = Node(6)  
tree.root.right.right = Node(7)
```

Implementing a BST

- Basic python code for creating a tree:

```
class Node(object):  
    def __init__(self, value):  
        self.value = value  
        self.left = None  
        self.right = None
```

```
class BinaryTree(object):  
    def __init__(self, root):  
        self.root = Node(root)
```

```
tree = BinaryTree(1)  
tree.root.left = Node(2)  
tree.root.right = Node(3)  
tree.root.left.left = Node(4)  
tree.root.left.right = Node(5)  
tree.root.right.left = Node(6)  
tree.root.right.right = Node(7)
```


BST: Moodle Code

- BSTs are notoriously difficult to visualize / print
- If you try `print(tree)` – this results in gobbledegook
- If you try `print(list(tree))` - gobbledegook
- So basic code for creating a tree, as well as the much more complex code for printing it, comes 'for free' – you don't have to worry about it
- It's on Moodle in the 'BASIC BST CODE' folder

Implementing Search

- There are different ways to do BST search, as we have seen (BFS, DFS)
- Over is some basic search pseudocode

Basic BST Search Pseudocode (Iterative)

```
BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target)
  cur_node ← tree.root
  WHILE cur_node ≠ ∅
    IF cur_node.value = target
      RETURN cur_node (or TRUE)(or cur_node.value)
    ELSE IF cur_node.value > target
      cur_node ← cur_node.left
    ELSE
      cur_node ← cur_node.right
  RETURN FALSE
```

//note that BST code is object oriented.

//that means 'self' is the argument rather than 'tree';

//tree is the object this method works on

Basic BST Search Pseudocode (Iterative)

```
BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target)
  cur_node ← tree.root
  WHILE cur_node ≠ ∅
    IF cur_node.value = target
      RETURN cur_node (or TRUE)(or cur_node.value)
    ELSE IF cur_node.value > target
      cur_node ← cur_node.left
    ELSE
      cur_node ← cur_node.right
  RETURN FALSE
```

//note that BST code is object oriented.

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Basic BST Search Pseudocode (Iterative)

```
BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target)
  cur_node ← tree.root
  WHILE cur_node ≠ ∅
    IF cur_node.value = target
      RETURN cur_node (or TRUE)(or cur_node.value)
    ELSE IF cur_node.value > target
      cur_node ← cur_node.left
    ELSE
      cur_node ← cur_node.right
  RETURN FALSE
```

//note that BST code is object oriented.

//that means 'self' is the argument rather than 'tree';

//tree is the object this method works on

Basic BST Search Pseudocode (Iterative)

```
BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target)
  cur_node ← tree.root
  WHILE cur_node ≠ ∅
    IF cur_node.value = target
      RETURN cur_node (or TRUE)(or cur_node.value)
    ELSE IF cur_node.value > target
      cur_node ← cur_node.left
    ELSE
      cur_node ← cur_node.right
  RETURN FALSE
```

//note that BST code is object oriented.

//that means 'self' is the argument rather than 'tree';

//tree is the object this method works on

Basic BST Search Pseudocode (Recursive)

BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target)

IF tree.root

if tree._BIN-TREE-FIND(target, tree.root)

RETURN True

RETURN False

ELSE

RETURN None

_BIN-TREE-FIND(tree, target, cur_node)

IF target > cur_node.data AND cur_node.right

RETURN tree._BIN-TREE-FIND(target, cur_node.right)

ELSE IF target < cur_node.data AND cur_node.left

RETURN tree._BIN-TREE-FIND(target, cur_node.left)

IF target == cur_node.data

RETURN True

BST Deletion

- Deletion is more complex.
- Your **first advanced viva task** (of 3) will be to implement node deletion into the existing BST code on Moodle. This task will be launched in Week 5.
- You will be fully supported with pseudocode and a partial implementation in Python

Summary

- We've looked at BSTs: Binary Search Trees
- Topologies, rules
- Traverse / search, insert, delete
- A heads-up on AVL, used to balance trees
- A balanced BST is fast to search, insert, and delete